

EFFECT OF MARINE ENVIRONMENT ON THE MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF FRP-STEEL JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

Fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites have been increasingly used in the repair of steel pipelines, mainly attributed to the superior material's properties. The advantages of FRP composites include their lightness, corrosion and environmental resistance, high mechanical strength, high stiffness, and low maintenance cost. These advantages have been explored by the oil and gas industry, where topside steel pipelines are often exposed to harsh marine environments characterized by high relative humidity and saline atmosphere. This research aims to evaluate the effects of temperature and saline environment on the steel-composite joint system and their interface. Specimens prepared with various surface configurations were subjected to accelerated aging in salt-spray chambers at temperatures of 35 °C, 55 °C and 70 °C. The results reported include composite water sorption and joint double lap shear strength with time. Lastly, strength degradation model was evaluated.

KEYWORDS

Water sorption, mechanical performance, degradation curves

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of FRP repairs systems has significantly grown in marine environment, particularly in offshore industries, due to the great physical, chemical and mechanical properties (Budhe et al., 2018; Li et al., 2019; Shamsuddoha et al., 2013). The FRP composites commonly employed in the offshore pipe's steel repair system are carbon fiber-reinforced composites (CFRP) and glass fiber-reinforced composites (GFRP). The composite repairs have several advantages, as simple manufacturing and installation, low production cost and low strength-to-weight ratio (Nguyen et al., 2012; Shamsuddoha et al., 2013), although also presented some disadvantages, such as their susceptibility to environmental degradation (i.e., humidity and moderate/high temperature).

The primary type of specimen configuration used to study the effects of hygrothermal aging on bond strength and adhesion properties of the pipe system were adhesively bonded joints with polymer-based adhesives. The hygrothermal aging can causes degradation of FRP/steel joints through main three

forms: (i) the composite material or the adhesive layer itself, (ii) the composite/adhesive interface, (iii) and steel/adhesive interface. During hygrothermal aging, the water ingresses mostly by diffusion through the adhesive, through capillarity at the adhesive/adherent interfaces, and last, through cracks and voids, depending on degradation stage of the system. The aging composite and adhesive layer usually present plasticization and hydrolysis of the matrix (Ascione et al., 2021), and in an advanced stage of degradation, material swelling and cracks (Costa et al., 2005; Heshmati et al., 2016; Xu Jiang et al., 2014; Robert et al., 2010; Shamsuddoha et al., 2017; Zafar et al., 2012). Additionally, with respect to adhesive/adherent interface, the water presence of water may lead to irreversible damage such as debonding and chemical attack (Dawood & Rizkalla, 2010; Heshmati et al., 2015, 2016).

The performance of the FRP/steel joint has been the subject of extensive research on the last years. A review presented by Karbhari (Karbhari & Shulley, 1995) and Heshmati et al. (Heshmati et al., 2015) demonstrated the variety of studies that have been conducted so far on this topic. It was observed a general trend of decrease in lap shear strength, single lap shear (SLS), double lap shear (DLS) and others configurations, when exposed to various aging conditions (Agarwal et al., 2014; Dawood & Rizkalla, 2010; Heshmati et al., 2015, 2016, 2017a; Karbhari & Shulley, 1995; Nguyen et al., 2012). For example, Heshmati et al. (Heshmati et al., 2017a) evaluated steel/FRP joints exposed to different environment and observed a loss of strength even within a short period of time in glass-fiber composite joints. GFRP/steel joints presented 20% and 41% of strength reduction at 20 °C and 45 °C, respectively, after one year of immersion in salt-water. A general observation was that higher temperatures lead to a greater reduction in strength, particularly in the case of GFRP systems compared to CFRPs.

A number of studies have also reported changes in the failure mode of FRP-steel joints with different hygrothermal aging's scenarios (Agarwal et al., 2014, 2015; Al-Shawaf et al., 2009; Heshmati et al., 2017a; X. Jiang et al., 2015; Nguyen et al., 2011, 2013; Roy et al., 2000; Teixeira de Freitas et al., 2017; Y. Wang et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2005). The aging joint specimens usually presented adhesive failure (steel/adhesive and FRP/adhesive interface, while the non-aged exhibit cohesive failure (Agarwal et al., 2015; Dawood & Rizkalla, 2010; Heshmati et al., 2017b; Nguyen et al., 2012; Roy et al., 2000; Teixeira de Freitas et al., 2017; Y. Wang et al., 2018). In this context, Freitas et al. (Teixeira de Freitas et al., 2017) suggested that a longer exposure time increased the percentage of adhesive failure, which indicates an increasing interfacial degradation. In this study, 14% and 23% reductions in the adhesion performance were observed after 30 and 90 days, respectively, for exposure to salt spray.

Considering the strength of the joint, the FRPs/steel joints system can be enhanced through various surface treatment methods. For example, some procedures applied to steel substrate are sand blasting (SB), grit blasting (GB), silane treatment and chemical coatings. All surface treatments demonstrate efficiency to increase fracture toughness to some extent (Monden et al., 2016). ISO 24817:2017 (INTERNATIONAL STANDARD, 2017) also recommends the cleaning and degreasing of the substrate to remove contaminants (Encinas et al., 2012; Prolongo & Ureña, 2009) and a abrasion of the surface. The standard specifies that a chemical treatment can also be used to improve the resistance of the interface. The most usual surface treatments for steel substrates is GB (Heshmati et al., 2015). Its application results in a clean and textured surface, enhancing the bond strength and overall performance of the FRP composite system. Additionally, other methods have been used in combination to grit-blasting to improve the bond integrity and its environmental stability (Harris & Beevers, 1999). For example, Wang et al. (B. Wang et al., 2017) reported an improvement of adhesive bonding of grit-blasted steel substrates with some additional methods combinations, such as ultrasonic cleaning (UC) surface and resin pre-coating (PC). Comparing the results of the bond strengths obtained from the various treatments, using GB treatment as reference, it was observed that GB/UC, GB/PC and GB/UC/PC, presented improvements of 8%, 25% and 32%, respectively.

Numerous studies have successfully demonstrated the improvement of joints properties using silane coupling agents (Al-Shawaf et al., 2009; Dawood & Rizkalla, 2010; Del Real et al., 2011; Heshmati et al., 2015; Yu et al., 2018). Silanes, as monomeric silicone-based chemicals, possess functional groups that undergo chemical reactions with the organic functional groups present in the adhesive and the inorganic functional groups on the steel surface, which likely leads to an enhanced adhesive/adherent chemical bond (Yu et al., 2018). In Dawood and Rizkalla (Dawood & Rizkalla, 2010) study, it was

observed that joints untreated with silane exhibited a 60% degradation in bond strength, whereas the silane-treated specimens showed no signs of degradation even after 6 months of exposure to seawater immersion. More recently, the study conducted by Borrie et al. (Borrie et al., 2021) confirmed these observations. The steel-CFRP double-lap joints were prepared using different combinations of epoxy adhesives and silane pre-treatment, in 5% NaCl solutions at different temperatures. Silane coatings showed an improvement in strength and durability during environmental aging, resulting in a 7% and 17% increase in strength for Araldite 420 HM CFRP joints subject to 20 °C and 50 °C, respectively. In the experiments, generally it was observed that many specimens experienced failure due to fiber breakage or at the composite-adhesive interface, highlighting the silane's improvement adhesive properties of the metal-adhesive interface. Thus, around 35% of samples showed an improvement in strength from silane pretreatment (Borrie et al., 2021).

In this study, steel/composite double-lap shear (DLS) tests were conducted to investigate the impact of hygrothermal conditioning on its mechanical behavior, considering aging time, temperature and different surfaces treatments, including silane coating. The failure mechanism and residual properties were also evaluated, with the prediction of property retention using a degradation model.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Materials

The steel/composite double lap shear (DLS) joints were fabricated using a fiber reinforced polymer composites adhered to plates of ASTM A516 Gr 70 steel substrate. The specimens were fabricated with hand lay-up lamination and composed by epoxy resin reinforced with bidirectional E-glass reinforcement fabric (66 % longitudinal fibers and 33 % transverse fibers). The GFRP element properties were provided in Table 1.

Table 1: GFRP material properties

Properties	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elastic modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)	ILSS (MPa)
GFRP Composite	426,6 ± 28,3	28,0 ± 1,1	330,6 ± 24,1	24,3 ± 1,9	32,2 ± 2,3

Figure 1 illustrates the DLS joints fabricated, along with images of manufactured samples prior to hygrothermal aging. It is important to emphasize that epoxy resin was applied to coat the exposed lateral faces of the joints, in an attempt to ensure unidirectional diffusion.

b)

Figure 1: Double Lap Shear joints: a) specimens' dimensions; b) specimens prior to aging (dimensions in mm).

Additionally, the behavior of the joint was investigated for four different surface treatments: machine sanding without silane (M0), manual sanding without silane (L0), machine sanding with silane (MS), and manual sanding with silane (LS). A Silane was used for the chemical treatment. An epoxy-based adhesive was applied on the composite/adherent interface.

Method

Hygrothermal Aging

The samples underwent hygrothermal testing in hygrothermal chambers with saline conditions at temperatures of 35, 55, and 70 °C, for approximately 15,000 hours. The hygrothermal chambers were manufactured by *Equilam*, and operated with a consistently high relative humidity of 95%. They were also monitored during experimental program to maintain optimal conditions. Each period is equivalent to the aging time of a group of samples (number defined as normative standard for each test) until they are removed from respective conditioning chamber to be tested to verify their mechanical properties through destructive test. The salt concentration used in the hygrothermal chambers was 5.0% by weight. Finally, a standard terminology was created to indicated the temperature of conditioning specimens. The hygrothermal chambers A, B, C, corresponded to temperatures of 35 °C, 55 °C and 70 °C, respectively.

Double-lap shear test

The double-lap shear tests (DLS) were performed on the unaged and aged joints aiming to determine the shear strength of the adhesive joints over aging time. These tests were performed according to the recommendations of the ASTM D3528 standard (D3528-96, 2013). A universal tests machine MTS 311.11, with 1000kN capacity, were used for the experimental program. The test was conducted under displacement control with a rate of 1.3 mm/min, up to failure. Ten specimens for each surface treatment previously described, were analyzed in the conditions as-supplied and after conditioning (35°C, 55°C, 70°C). All the tests were carried out at room temperature (23 ± 2 °C).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Double lap shear test

Figures 2, 3 and 4 illustrate the box-plot graphs of the strength levels of the joints as a function of time for specimens conditioned in chambers at 35 °C (A), 55 °C (B) and 70 °C (C), respectively. The specimens in chamber A (Figure 2) presented a higher strength than the other chambers, which can indicate minor degradation at lower temperatures despite the moist environment, although the decreasing trend is evident for all samples. It was also observed that, starting from 3490 hours of aging, some specimens experienced failure before the tests could be conducted, indicating significant interface degradation. The most affected samples, clearly, were those exposed to 70 °C (chamber C). After 10170 hours, the majority of the samples had lost their integrity, with many breaking even before being tested. Finally, at 11840 hours, the resistance had dropped to levels below 20% of the reference value. The

results corroborate with those observed by other authors Karbhari (Karbhari & Shulley, 1995) and Heshmati et al. (Heshmati et al., 2015).

Figure 2: Boxplot of the average strength values for chamber A (35°C).

Figure 3: Boxplot of the average strength values for chamber B (55°C).

Figure 4: Boxplot of the average strength values for chamber C (70°C).

Additionally, the failure modes were evaluated. The unaged specimens failed at the steel/composite interface with adhesive failure, commonly observed for such type of unaged system (Agarwal et al., 2014, 2015; Al-Shawaf et al., 2009; Dawood & Rizkalla, 2010; Heshmati et al., 2016, 2017b; X. Jiang et al., 2015; Nguyen et al., 2011, 2012; Roy et al., 2000; Teixeira de Freitas et al., 2017; Y. Wang et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2005). The typical failure modes were: debonding of both sides of the same steel plate (Figure 5a), debonding of two bonded regions of different steel plates (Figure 5b) and debonding of three bonded faces (Figure 5c). The areas of detachment were indicated with white arrows in the images.

Figure 5: Failure modes observed in the unaged specimens: a) debonding of both sides of the same steel plate; b) debonding of two bonded regions of different steel plates; c) debonding of three bonded faces (failure surface of steel plate).

On the other hand, the aged samples showed a combination of cohesive failure (adhesive failure with retention of the adhesive on the metallic substrate) and adhesive failure (adhesive detachment from the substrate). These results are also in accordance with what has been observed by other studies (e.g de Freitas et al. (Teixeira de Freitas et al., 2017)), confirming that aging demonstrated an impact on the percentage of delaminated area of the samples, changing the failure mode.

Figure 6: Example of the failure modes obtained for the aged specimens.

Degradation model

In order to investigate the results obtained from DLS tests, a phenomenological model previously proposed by Phani and Bose (Phani & Bose, 1987) was used. The model was adapted, where the retention of mechanical properties, S , was used instead of the absolute strength value, as presented in Eq. 1.

$$S = (S_0 - S_\infty)e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} + S_\infty \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where S_0 is the initial strength of the unaged material, S_∞ is the strength after infinite time, t is the aging time in hours, and τ is the model's fitting parameter. The model is only valid when the degradation mechanism remains the same throughout the aging process and does not change with temperature.

Figure 7: Phani e Bose model adjustment for DLS joints strength results: a) L0, b) M0, c) LS, d) MS.

The results demonstrate that the highest property retentions were obtained for the lower temperatures. Regarding the type of surface treatment applied to the joints, the treatment MS showed the highest retention values, with a retention above 60% according to the model's trend for samples conditioned in the chamber A (35°C). On the other hand, the lowest retention value for the same condition was obtained with treatment M0, with a retention slightly above 20%. This result indicates that the application of *silane* coupling agent appears to be a factor that influences property retention, at least for the temperature of 35°C (the lowest temperature evaluated). This is also evidenced in the comparative results between the property retentions of treatments L0 and LS in specimens exposed to 35 °C, where LS maintained a higher retention value than L0. For specimens exposed to 55 °C, and 70 °C, the treatment did not prove to be a significant factor for the final results. Thus, the obtained result is aligned with many studies (Al-Shawaf et al., 2009; Dawood & Rizkalla, 2010; Del Real et al., 2011; Heshmati et al., 2015; Yu et al., 2018), which indicates an increase in the bonding properties of FRP/steel joints, although some questions still remain. As related in Borrie *et al.* (Borrie et al., 2021) research, in some cases, depending on the failure mode, the improvement of the bond property of FRP/steel may not be evident. Therefore, a definitive conclusion still depends on further investigations.

4. CONCLUSION

In summary, the specimens in chamber C (70 °C) showed lower mechanical properties at end of experiment, indicating higher degradation at higher temperatures. Some specimens experienced premature failure due to interface failure after 3490 hours of aging, for all scenarios. The failure modes differed between unaged and aged samples, with adhesive and cohesive failures observed in the aged samples. The results showed that property retentions were highest at lower temperatures. The treatment MS exhibited the highest retention values, while treatment M0 had the lowest retention values at 35°C. Silane was identified as a factor influencing property retention primarily at lower temperatures.

However, for specimens exposed to 55°C and 70°C, the treatment did not have a significant impact on the results.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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